

GROWTH OF TOURISM AND EMPLOYMENT POTENTIAL ON HOTEL INDUSTRIES IN VELLORE DISTRICT - A HISTORICAL ANALYSIS

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Introduction:

Tourism is a complex industry that involves a broad range of business, organizations and government agencies working together at different levels to deliver a complete tourism experience. Each party in the chain contributes to the overall holiday experience of the customer from initial destination marketing through to the ground level experience. It is a collection of activities, services and industries that delivers a travel experience, including transportation, accommodations and boarding and a living tradition of music, dance, folk arts and fine arts. Vellore District is well renowned for its temple towns and heritage sites, hill stations, waterfalls, national parks, local cuisine and the fabulous wildlife and scenic beauty. It is the most popular tourist destination and the second-highest district for foreign arrivals from the States of Tamil Nadu. Its combined aggregate gives it the most popular state for tourism.

The Ancient history of Vellore shows that battle field where the warriors used to fight was left with abandoned weapons like spears. The name Vellore is also said to have been derived from some form of precious stone which had a similar sounding name. There is megalithic proto-historical evidence in and around Vellore of such a semi-precious stone industry being prevalent in ancient times.

Vellore has a blend of heritage and culture reflecting the ancient Dravidian civilization. It was the seat of the Pallavas, Cholas, Nayak, Marathas, Arcot Nawabs and Bijapur Sultan Kingdoms. Vellore was once the capital city of the Vijayanagar Empire during 1606-1672. The fort in Vellore was described as the best and strongest fortress during the Carnatic War in the 17th Century. The monuments found in the district give a vivid picture of the evolution of the city through the ages. The north and south regions of Arcot came into the political map in 1810 at the time of the last Mughal Emperor. Later in 1908, the two districts, namely North and South Arcot came into existence. Chittoor (now in Andhra Pradesh) was the first capital of the North Arcot district. From then on it was the principal military base of the British. In 1911, Vellore became the head quarters of North Arcot Dt., comprising Vellore and Thiruvannamalai.

Located at the banks of the Palar River, Vellore is an ancient city that has been ruled by the various prosperous dynasties of south India. The Pallavas, The Cholas, Vijaynagar kingdom, Carnatic Empire and the British are the various powers that ruled the region of Vellore and are responsible for the city's cultural heritage. The city like any princely Indian city should be is famous for various forts, temples, picnic spots and other important tourist attractions. So here's the list of the most important places to visit in Vellore.

Tourism:

Vellore is a biggest explosives tourist places and famous tourism places are located in the heart of the city is the biggest private employer in the city. It creates a large floating population, mostly from other states of Tamil Nadu. Lodging, hospitality and allied businesses are among major sources of income generated in the central part of the city. With the advent of hospitals such as Apollo KH Hospitals, Melvisharam and Sri Narayani Medical Research Centre, Ariyur and colleges such as CMC, VIT and other engineering and science colleges, hospitality industry is growing at a rampant pace. Also, the city is known for its huge expatriate population scattered around the State which forms major source of wealth. Sripuram in the southern tip of the city has interestingly cajoled up at lot of tourism interests in city and the surrounding areas Golden Temple, Jalakanteswarar Temple, Elagiri Lake, Palar Anaicut Dam, Kavalur Observatory, Tippu Mahal, Delhi Gate, Mordhana Dam, Jalagamparai and Jalagamparai Water Falls.

Vellore Fort:

Vellore Fort is situated in heart of the Vellore city in the state of Tamil Nadu, India built by Vijayanagara Kings. The Fort was at one point of time the headquarters of the Aravidu Dynasty of Vijayanagara Empire. The fort is known for its grand ramparts, wide moat and robust masonry. The Fort's ownership passed from Vijayanagara Kings, to the Bijapur Sultans, to Marathas, to the Carnatic Nawabs and finally to the British, who held the fort until India gained independence. The Indian government maintains the Fort with the Archaeological Department. During British rule, the Tipu Sultan's family and the last king of Sri Lanka, Sri Vikrama Rajasinha was held in as prisoners in the fort. The fort houses a Christian church, a Muslim mosque and a Hindu temple, the latter of which is famous for its magnificent carvings. The first rebellion against British

rule erupted at this fort in 1806, and it is also a witness to the massacre of the Vijayanagara royal family of Sriranga Raya.

Government Museum:

Government museum is located inside the Vellore fort in Lakshmanswami town hall. It is a multipurpose museum having a great collection of different types of artifacts like archeology, history, geology and botany also. The museum is open all days except government holidays. Museum has 2896 exhibits, both displayed and reserved. Museum has 8 galleries which are District Gallery, Stone sculpture Gallery, Pre-History-Philately Gallery, Paintings Gallery, Zoology Gallery, Bronze Gallery, Coins Gallery and Anthropology Gallery.

Science Park:

Vellore Science Park (also known as Vellore District Science Centre) located in Sathuvachari east part of the Vellore City. This science centre is among the four centres in Tamil Nadu developed by Tamil Nadu Science and Technology centre. It has number of galleries including on environment; leather and physical science. Objective of the science park is to enable children learn science through play method. Science Park here had made it possible for the students and general public to view comet ISON with its telescopic facility on 28 November 2013. Science Park also conducts summer camps for students teaching them on physics, chemistry, maths, biology, environmental sciences, yoga, psychology and also practical experiments. Proposal of 3D theatre at Vellore Science Park has been initiated on March, 2013. If plans go expected, Vellore will be the only city other than Chennai in Tamil Nadu to have this facility. It would be an added attraction for students which would make watching various scientific phenomena come alive, almost real and the movies will be sourced from National Museum of Natural History, USA, would deal with concepts of cloning, life cycles, dinosaur, exploration of life, space mission, astronomy, solar system, mystic animals, and the lives of scientists.

Vainu Bappu Observatory:

The Vainu Bappu Observatory is an astronomical observatory owned and operated by Indian Institute of Astrophysics. It is located in the Javadi Hills Kavalur, near Vaniyambadi & Yelagiri and its around 70 km from Vellore City. Vainu Bappu Observatory (also known as Kavalur Astronomical observatory) is home to the Vainu Bappu Telescope, the largest telescope in Asia. It has a diameter of 2.3 meters and was first used in 1986. Along with the Vainu Bappu telescope, the observatory has two other telescopes.

Amirthi Forest and Zoological Park:

Amirthi Forest & Zoological Park is situated under the javadu hills of tellai across Amirthi River which is 25 km from Vellore. The area of the park is 25 hectares and one can find beautiful waterfalls. Half of this jungle is cleared to serve as a tourist spot while the other half is developed as a wildlife sanctuary. Animals at the park include spotted deer, mongoose, hedgehog, foxes, monkey, red headed parrots, love birds, tortoises, peacock, crocodiles, wild cats, eagles, ducks, pigeons, wild parrots, rabbits, and pythons.

Sri Lakshmi Golden Temple:

The golden temple of *Sripuram* is a spiritual park situated at the foot of a small range of green hills in a place known as "Malaikodi" in the city of Vellore. The temple is located between Vellore-Odugathur state highway and at the southern end of the city of Vellore, at Tirumalaikodi. The temple is located on 100 acres of land and has been constructed by Vellore-based *Sri Narayani Peedam*, headed by spiritual leader *Sri Sakthi Amma* also known as *Narayani Amma*. The temple with gold covering has intricate work done by artisans specializing in temple art using gold. *Sripuram* design represents a star-shaped path (Sri Chakra), positioned in the middle of the lush green landscape, with a length of over 1.8 km. One has to walk along the star path to reach the temple in the middle, which has messages laid out along the path to the temple from *Sri Sakthi Amma*, Gita, Bible and Quran. When one enters the *Sripuram*, their focus is just on the magnificent temple. But when they leave, they cannot do so without taking some messages and gaining some wisdom.

Jalakandeswarar Temple:

The Jalagandeswarar Temple, dedicated to Jalagandeeswarar, is noted for its sculptures, and speaks volumes of the exquisite craftsmanship of the highly skilled artisans of that period. The sculpture in the porch on the left of the entrance is a masterpiece appreciated by the connoisseurs of art and architecture. The temple was long used as an arsenal, and remained without a deity, although several years ago it was sanctified with an idol of Lord Shiva.

Vallimalai Sri Thenvenkatachalapathy Temple:

Sri Thenvenkatachalapathy temple is a Vedic temple in the down of the Vallimalai hill town near Thiruvallam in Vellore district of Tamil Nadu, India. It was located in Vellore district of Tamil Nadu. Vallimalai is present 25 km from Vellore and 12 km from Thiruvallam. According to history when Vishnu was in deep meditation Lakshmi came like deer and she plays in front of him. At that time Vishnu's meditation was dispersed and he saw that deer. Due to his holy glory a beautiful daughter was born both of them left their daughter for the sake of their devotee king. After that king found the child in Vallikilanku field so, she called as Valli. The idol is Swayambumurthi now he is growing on, also the special in that temple was for of devotees got child after praying in this temple.

Eelagiri Hills:

Elagiri is a hill station in Vellore, India, situated off the Vaniyambadi-Tirupattur road. Located at an altitude of 1,410.6 metres above Mean Sea Level and spread across the Yelagiri village (also spelled Elagiri at times) is surrounded by orchards, rose-gardens, and green valleys. The Elagiri hill station is not as developed as other hill stations in Tamil Nadu. However, the district administration has now taken up the task of developing Yelagiri Hills into a tourist destination by promoting adventure sports such as paragliding and rock climbing. Places of attraction in Yelagiri are artificial lake, Jalagamparai.

Arrivals of Tourists:

Tamil Nadu stands second next to Maharashtra in Foreign tourist arrivals, and third in domestic Tourist Arrivals and Minister. The Minister attributed the increase in the flow to aggressive promotion and marketing campaigns, creation and up gradation of basic amenities and infrastructure at tourist spots have resulted in the increase. He noted Vision 2023 envisages an investment of Rs 10,000 crore in Tourism and Hospitality sectors through Government and Private investments by 2023. The foreign tourist arrivals targeted for 2023 is 15 million tourists. The Number of tourist arrival in the state rose by 34.1 per cent in 2012 to 187.6 million from 140 million. Meanwhile, to boost the sector further the Government is formulating a new Tourism Policy and to take up Rs 500 crore worth project, with Asian Development Bank (ADB's) assistance. The Minister for Tourism, Tamil Nadu Government said that tourist arrivals in 2012 was 187.6 million, includes 184.1 million domestic and 3.5 million foreign tourists, as compared to 140 million (includes 136.7 million and 3.3 million foreign) in 2011 and 105.8 million in 2010 includes 103 million and 2.8 million domestic and foreign tourists respectively.

Growth Tourism:

The foreign tourist arrivals is 2044 in 2001, 8600 in 2005, 20783 in 2010 and 89253 in 2015 tourists. The Number of tourist arrival in the district rose by 34.1 per cent in during 2001 to 2015. The arrivals of foreign tourist in the Vellore District has been clearly seen that clearly increasing year by year, as Chennai is leading from the transport facilities through the Chennai airport facilities due to this it has been core place for the travelers to visit and continue their trip from Chennai to Vellore.

The Domestic tourists arrivals in 30514 in 2001, 51058 in 2005, 1002384 in 2010 and 3013248 in 2015 from them majority of domestic arrivals has the pilgrimage visiting for famous Temples and festivals. Remaining of the visitor in the summer season when tourists visited in the hill stations and beaches, as there is high level of improvement in the district.

District Hotel Management and Catering Technology Vellore has been functioning celebrating fairs and festivals to attract tourists and implementing the projects of the Centre for the benefits of tourists visiting the district, the tourism department also offers concessions and incentives by way of subsidies to hotel projects. Through publicity promotion and marketing wing, concerted efforts have been taken to attract more tourists and through advertisements in various media. The increasing trend of domestic and foreign tourist's arrivals of district from 2001 to 2015 it has shown the growth rate is 3.4 of tourist's arrivals in domestic and foreign. It has increased up to 2012 whereas it shows a decreasing rate in 2013, but in 2014 the growth rate has boosted up to 21 % and it reaches 34 % of growth rate in 2015.

Hotel Industry:

The development of hotel industry is continuous and satisfactory. The British introduced hotels in India mainly for their own use or for foreign visitors. The hotels in Vellore District were owned and operated by Arabian Hotels, Victory Hotel and the Hope Hall in this arrangement in an excellent one.

Categories of Hotels:

Besides the star hotels, categorized and discussed, other types of hotels cater to the demands of increasing number of tourists. Different types of hotels are explained manner.

Palace Hotels:

The concept of hotels making in to the magnificent palaces of famous turned into luxury. It convert to Palace into a hotel Maharaja of Jaipur was the next one to convert his Ram Bagh Palace into a hotel. The Maharaja of Udaipur was the third one to the Rajasthan the Jodhpur Palace, the Jaywalker Palace and the Bikaner Palace were also converted into hotels. Palaces by themselves are great attractions to tourists. They can get an opportunity to stay in these palaces and enjoy like Maharajas. Palaces of the former princes in India are now serving as five-star hotels are more than twenty palaces are now five star hotels. The Indian Tobacco Company (ITC) entered the hotel industry in 1957 with the opening of the Chola. All hotels of ITC are named after the famous period of dynasties of history. It has plans to have in devotees. Welcome group chain of ITC has seventeen hotels in India also have floating hotels in the form of house boats are very popular and heritage tourists.

Heritage Hotels:

A new classification standard of heritage hotels has been introduced to cover functioning hotels in palaces, hovels, castles, forts and residences built prior to 1950. As the traditional structure reflects the ambience and lifestyle of the b) gone era, it is immensely popular with the tourists. The scheme is aimed to

ensure that such properties, landmarks of our heritage are not lost due to decay and disuse; at the same time, by bringing such properties into the approved sector, they become financially viable besides providing additional room capacity for the tourist.

Hospitality implies friendly reception and warm greetings. Guests arriving at the Plaza Hotels in New York City find French perfume and chilled champagne waiting in their rooms. At the Bangkok Regal guests wake every morning to find their shoes perfectly shined. At the Hotel Plaza Paris the staff remembers the name of every client upon arrival. At the Maintaining and resort in departing clients are serenaded with a melodic song performed by the hotel staff. All these are images of hospitality of warm greetings, fine accommodations and friendly actions. Hospitality is merely a tradition fit is a way of life.

Accommodation:

Accommodation for travelers may be conveniently viewed in two ways. The traveler who left his home required accommodation at his destination and for journeys, which cannot be completed in a single day. Hence the traveler is in need of overnight accommodation. Inns were perhaps the first such accommodation units which catered to the needs of travellers in early times in Britain. This type of Inn keeping has been a very ancient process. In olden days and during the rule of Roman Empire many such Inns were established which provided food, drink and also entertainment to weary travelers. Subsequently people travelled very infrequently for trading and hence inn keeping lost its importance. There are more than hundred years old coaching and posting inns operating in England as hotels, as part of Trust House.

Holiday Inns:

The first holiday inn hotel spans the world from USA through Europe, the Mediterranean, Africa, Asia and the Middle East to Australia opened under the franchise from Holiday Inns. Incorporated USA the seven star hotel is the venture of the Eastern International Hotels Ltd, The holiday Inn hotels have their system in the world largest computerized global reservation network that would enable its customers to make reservation in Holiday Inns anywhere in the world, at almost free of cost.

International Hotels:

These are modern western style hotels situated in the big cities as well as at the important tourist centers. These are from one to five star hotels classified according to the international Standard and accepted star system of hotels. These hotels provide accommodation restaurants, gym rooms, beauty parlors, bars, special suits, which are integral part of their business. These hotels belong to the luxury class hotels. Such type of hotels caters to the need of holiday maker tourists and those who, by reason of health desire a change of atmosphere. Resort hotels are located near the mountains or other area having natural beauty. Rest, relaxation and comfort are the main factors around which hotels are built. The resort hotels are built in order to give the visitor a special welcome and a homely atmosphere.

Commercial Hotels:

This type of hotels is direct appeal mainly to the individual traveler as compared to the international or resort hotels where the focus is on group travel. Most of the commercial hotels receive guests who are on business tours although some are permanent guests. As these hotels cater to the needs of the people who are visiting a place for business or trade, these are generally located in important commercial and industrial centers of big cities.

Residential Hotels:

Residential hotels are also known as apartment hotels, Room charges can be paid monthly, yearly or yearly basis. These hotels were first developed in the vicinity where people realized that permanent living in a hotel is very dangerous. These hotels are located in big cities.

Motels:

Motels are located on the high ways is highly automatic with minimum personal and offering prices at the lower end of its class. It is inexpensive, easy to manage, involves economy on labour and maintenance. Simply motel is a type of accommodation that is relaxation to the people travelling- on roads for long distances by car or vans.

Floating Hotels:

Floating hotels are located on the water surface like, sea, rivers or lakes. The services provided in a hotel are also present in this type. These hotels are popular in many countries. Sometimes luxury ships have been converted into floating hotels after proving very popular among the tourists. These provide an exclusive and exotic atmosphere. Floating hotels in the form of houseboats are very popular with tourists.

Supplementary Accommodation:

Supplementary accommodation plays a very important role in the total available tourist accommodation in a country. This caters to both international as well as domestic tourist traffic. The main types of supplementary accommodation are the Marriage Halls and Travelers Bungalows in tourist spots. These can be obtained at a low cost for the lower income group tourists.

Saris and Dharmasalas:

Saris known as inns were built by kings or the elite, on both sides of the roads where adequate arrangements were made for food, water and shelter for the convenience and comfort of the travelers, pilgrims, merchants, traders and also the state officials. These saris are continuing even today in some parts of the country with some improvement and innovations. Dharmasalas are many at religious centers. These accommodations are mainly useful for the group of tourists, especially for low-income people.

Youth Hostels:

Youth hostel movement is an international organization, which provides boarding and lodging for students and youth. These are located in major cities and are well equipped to provide accommodation to young men and women. These provide the boarding and lodging at a very low cost, with a place to rest and relax, eat and sleep or even prepare their own food. The services provided include accommodation, food and also recreation. The charges for the services are very nominal. These hostels are also equipped to enable users to prepare their own food if they take to do so. The accommodation provided in the youth hostels is for a limited number of days.

The types of hostels are special non-luxury inexpensive. Such types of hostels are very popular. These hostels are in various shapes and sizes and are located near churches. Students may also avail these hostels for their accommodations as dormitory accommodation is provided.

Caravans and Camping Sites:

These form an important accommodation category in many holiday areas. These are also known as open-air hostels, tourist camps or camping grounds. Camping was basically practiced by nomads on foot. Now it is largely giving way to car camping. The sites are usually located within the large cities in open spaces, when equipped to receive. Mobile accommodation is the form of car caravans. The camping sites provide facilities for parking, tent-pitching, water electricity toilets etc. The services provided generally include restaurants recreational rooms, toilets and at certain sites a grocers shops also.

Circuit Houses:

Accommodation in these houses is provided to the bona fide tourist possessing tourist cards. These houses provide the services of a cook and an attendant. It is not have the benefits of any special location, size or space, but it has shown the way for others as to how the provision of basic amenities and a high degree of efficient management can enable to serve effectively. Circuit Houses are at Kancheepuram, Sriperumpudur etc.

Tourist Holiday Village:

These villages are situated at warm sea sides and in the areas which provide certain facilities for the tourists. Tourist villages are located in the regions, which are economically viable. The villages are mostly promoted by government, social organizations and also by tourist organizations. This type of accommodation is present along the shore line in Mammallapuram, Kovaiaam etc. Silver Sands Resorts near Mahabalipuram is one such example.

Tourist Bungalows:

This is an important type of accommodation included in the category of supplementary accommodation. These bungalows are situated at tourist centres for the benefit of tourists, budget travelers and the youth of the country and these coming from different countries. It is present in the Highways Department of Tiruvattur District, Ulundurpet, Thirukoilur, Cuddalore etc.

Pensions:

This type of accommodation is very popular which the tourists use extensively by the tourists. Pension is also described as a private hotel, a guesthouse or as a boarding house. Catering facilities are optional and are usually restricted to the residents. Many of them stay for a longer and such define periods as a week or a fortnight. The reservation of accommodation as made in advance pension accommodation is cheaper than hotel accommodation.

Bed and Breakfast Establishment:

This accommodation units catering for holiday makers as well as business travelers, this establishment provides only accommodation and breakfast and not the principal meals. These are usually in large town and cities along commercial and holiday routes and also resort areas.

Budget Hotels:

This segment of hotels constitutes the 3 star and 4 star classes of hotels. This concept has gained ground in the past few years mainly because of the rising disposable income with the India middle class. Corporate setting up of budget hotels enjoy lower capital cost and shorter gestation period of compared to setting up of 5 star hotels.

Corporate Hotels:

As the business segment is expanding at a fast pace, especially in the metros, many hotels are projecting themselves as "corporate hotels. The department of tourism has adopted a system of approving and

classifying, the hotels on the basis of the facilities and services provided by them. Apart from normal star categories, a new classification called "Heritage Hotels" was introduced during 2009.

Employment Potential:

Actually it is a very difficult task to estimate the direct and indirect on Vellore District during 2001. Hotel and Restaurant sector is Tourism sector. According to Economic Census 2000 there were 836 Hotel and Restaurant enterprises in the District, of these maximum number of hotels and restaurant enterprises. The census 1998 recorded 432 hotels and restaurant enterprises and the present employed in those enterprises were registered as 749 persons. Hotels in Vellore have helped in tourism promotion existing with coming up hotels works out to 226 in 2001. The revenue earned by hotels through luxury tax has increased from Rs. 35.3 lakhs in 2001 Rs. 82.0 lakhs in 2015. The Volume of business transaction by star Hotels in Vellore has increased from Rs. 39 lakhs in 2009 to Rs. 72 lakhs 2015. Hotels put together 70 percent of sales are paid by credit card in 2015. Hotels have provided job for 1,711 person's rural areas and to 1,959 persons in urban areas in Tamil Nadu in 2001. Hotels in Tamil Nadu have attracted domestic and, foreign tourists and these facts prove that hotels in Tamil Nadu play a vital role in tourism promotion

Conclusion:

Tourism is the temporary, short-term movement of people to destination outside the places where they normally live and work and their activities during the stay at each destination. Infrastructure facilities live accommodation and transport is well developed in the district is the key element in the tourism product and an essential component of tourism organization's definition of a tourist presupposes that the tourist must spend at least one night in the destination visited. In tourism in Vellore district indicates a central role that accommodations plays in a vital role. Accommodation, which caters to domestic and international tourist, is an important input which follows in to overall tourism system. Vellore District has a transportation system that connects all parts of tourist places. It is served by an extensive road network, providing links between urban centers, agricultural market places and rural areas. The study region has been significantly successful in its tourism efforts in creating a key platform for both domestic and foreign traffic. The entire region has vast untapped potential in tourist and its allied sectors and there is a lot of scope for its future development and promotion. The domestic growth of tourist arrivals was increased by 34.4 percent during 2001 to 2015. In Vellore District assertions the second largest tourism industry in Tamil Nadu with an annual growth rate of 16%. In 2012 Vellore District was occupied the second slot of Tamil Nadu in terms of domestic as well as foreign arrivals.

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